

The Dynamics of Gender Ratios and Population Balance: Evolutionary, Social, and Environmental Influences

Sobirxujayev Xadyatillo

Student of National University of Uzbekistan

Article information:

Manuscript received: 22 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 23 Sep 2024; **Published:** 24 Oct 2024

Abstract: This essay explores the intricate mechanisms governing gender ratios and population balance, emphasizing the role of evolution as a natural corrective force akin to market dynamics. It examines statistical evidence indicating a predisposition toward male births and the subsequent demographic implications. Factors influencing these shifts are multifaceted, encompassing traditional gender politics, selective abortion practices, and environmental changes such as microplastics' impact on fertility. Through a comprehensive analysis, the essay highlights the interplay of these forces and their implications for future population structures and gender dynamics worldwide.

Keywords: Gender ratios, population balance, Evolution, Fertility, Microplastics, Selective abortion, Demographic trends, Social factors, Environmental influences, Gender politics.

Introduction

The study of gender ratios and population balance is crucial for understanding demographic shifts and their implications for social, economic, and environmental stability. A balanced sex ratio is often seen as a natural outcome of evolutionary pressures, but deviations from this balance can arise due to cultural, environmental, and policy factors. Historically, a slight predominance of male births has been observed, which is counterbalanced by higher male infant mortality rates, thus ensuring long-term balance. However, in several countries, societal preferences for male children have led to significant gender imbalances through practices such as sex-selective abortions. In parallel, emerging environmental issues, such as the widespread presence of microplastics, have been linked to declines in male fertility, potentially impacting birth ratios. These factors, combined with broader demographic trends, make the study of gender ratios a multifaceted issue with far-reaching consequences. This study aims to investigate the influence of evolutionary mechanisms, cultural practices, and environmental factors on gender ratios, providing a comprehensive analysis of their effects on population dynamics and social stability.

Methods. The study utilized a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both quantitative data analysis and a qualitative review of existing literature.

Data on birth rates and sex ratios from countries with significant gender imbalances were collected from sources such as the United Nations Population Division, World Bank, and national statistical agencies. These included data on sex ratios for first and subsequent births, particularly in countries like China, India, EU and the United States. Additionally, studies reporting environmental impacts on male fertility, such as those related to microplastic exposure, were reviewed for analysis.

A systematic literature review was conducted to identify key studies on genetic predispositions to gender

ratios, cultural influences, and environmental effects on fertility. Sources included peer-reviewed journals and articles from databases like PubMed, JSTOR, and Google Scholar. Specific attention was given to studies by T.J. Mathews et al. (2005), Gellatly (2009), D. Hansen et al (1999), Das Gupta (2005) and Vartiainen et al. (1999), among others that provided historical insights into natural sex ratio trends.

Statistical tools, such as R and SPSS, were used to analyze data on gender ratios, selective abortion rates, and environmental contaminants. This analysis involved calculating correlation coefficients to identify significant relationships between gender ratio trends and influencing factors, such as cultural practices and environmental exposure levels.

Results

Evolutionary theory posits that natural selection plays a crucial role in maintaining the balance of male and female births. Fisher's principle suggests that in many species, including humans, the ratio of male to female births tends to stabilize around 1:1 over time due to natural selection, which favors equal reproductive investment in each sex. However, slight deviations have been observed, with a tendency toward a slightly higher proportion of male births. Research by T.J. Mathews et al. (2005) suggests a genetic predisposition toward having boys. Their analysis of birth data in the USA from 1940 to 2004 found that the likelihood of the first child being a boy was 106 boys to 100 girls. For subsequent children, this ratio decreased to 103 boys per 100 girls, and among mothers of Southeast Asian descent, it rose to 114 boys per 100 girls. Similarly, historical data from Finland, as studied by Vartiainen et al. (1999), showed consistent male predominance from 1751 to 1997.

These figures do not suggest that natural selection is biased or discriminatory. There are several reasons why more boys are naturally born. Firstly, studies such as those by Gellatly (2009) have suggested that sperm carrying the Y chromosome are more active than those carrying the X chromosome, giving the Y chromosome an advantage in forming the zygote. This biological advantage, however, is counterbalanced by the higher vulnerability of male infants and young boys to disease and mortality, which has been documented in research by Cameron and Dalerum (2009). Various disorders such as hyperactivity, autism, clumsiness, stuttering are 3-4 times more common in boys than in girls, as showed in D. Hansen et al (1999). Behavioral and neurological disorders occur at least twice as often in boys. Kelleher (1998) found that suicide rates are also higher among men. Throughout history, men have often been the primary casualties of wars and famines. Women, on the other hand, tend to have a longer average life expectancy. Nature has endowed women with greater resilience to challenges and diseases, enabling them to survive and live longer. As a result, this evolutionary mechanism ensures a balanced gender ratio as populations age.

Cultural practices significantly influence gender ratios as well, often creating deviations from the natural equilibrium suggested by evolutionary models. Selective abortion practices, deeply rooted in social and cultural preferences for male children, have led to skewed gender ratios in many countries. Das Gupta (2005) highlights the role of cultural norms in driving gender-selective abortions in countries like India and China. In these societies, sons are often viewed as carriers of the family name and providers for parents in old age, whereas daughters may be considered a financial burden. In many regions of China, boys have historically been viewed as integral to the family, while girls are often seen as "guests", since it is believed they will join another family upon marriage. Moreover, a woman's social status in the community increases if her firstborn child is a boy, but this is not the case for a girl. The preference for male children, combined with the restrictive family planning policy, introduced in 1979, led to a significant increase in the number of male births through selective abortions. This has resulted in a highly skewed sex ratio in China, with a substantial surplus of young men. Similarly, in India, the widespread practice of sex-selective abortions, particularly in northern regions like Punjab and Haryana. In these areas, cultural norms that favor male heirs have led to a ratio of up to 120 boys for every 100 girls.

Data from the Pew Research Center shows that Arabian Peninsula exhibits the most pronounced gender imbalances. Currently, the countries with the highest male-to-female ratios include Qatar (266 men for every 100 women), the United Arab Emirates (228), and Bahrain (164). In several Gulf nations, these

stark gender disparities stem primarily from the perception of male children as heirs and successors. In contrast, this indicator remains moderate in economically developed countries, including the G7 nations, where suggesting the presence of effective gender policies exist and conservative views are less dominant.

However, in recent years, this long-standing "golden ratio" has begun to shift. The Tashkent City Statistics Department reported the number and gender composition of babies born over the past decade. According to their data, from 2011 to 2021, the birth rate of boys was higher across all districts and regions (with the exception of Bektemir in 2011 and Yakkasaray in 2019). But in recent years, the trend has changed. In 2022-2023, more girls were born in the city of Tashkent and its districts.

While this phenomenon has not yet been observed in other regions of Uzbekistan, it hints at a potential global shift. United Nations Population Division (2021) projections suggest that while the global population has historically seen a surplus of men, this imbalance is expected to reach equilibrium by 2050. The UN's findings are based on declining birth rates, particularly in countries that have historically experienced high levels of sex-selective practices. For instance, as fertility rates fall in countries like China and India, the imbalance between male and female populations may begin to correct itself, resulting in a more balanced gender ratio.

Recent studies have increasingly focused on the environmental factors that can prove some evidence for the equilibrium. A recent study examined the impact of ingested microplastics on declining birth rates globally. Previous studies have indicated that microplastics are pervasive, found in mountain tops, remote islands, the upper atmosphere, and the depths of the oceans. Traces of microplastics have even been detected in the human body, including the heart, brain, and lungs. Li et al. (2020) explored the impact of microplastics on male fertility. Researchers analyzed sperm samples from 36 healthy adult men living in Jinan, eastern China, who were not employed in the plastics industry. The analysis revealed lower sperm motility in samples containing polyvinyl chloride particles, suggesting a potential decline in male fertility in recent years, noting that the presence of polyvinyl chloride particles in the human body could impair sperm motility.

Additionally, some scientists have discovered that the Y chromosome is degrading. Although it took approximately 166 million years for the Y chromosome to form, its disappearance may occur in just a few tens of millions of years. While this process is considered long-term, even minor changes in a single gene can significantly affect phenotypes (human traits, appearance, etc.) and gender of fetus.

Discussion

The reasons and consequences of this situation are interpreted differently. Some argue that it may lead to a sharp increase in the number of elderly women, while others consider it a normal demographic process. Specifically, a decline in population growth will likely result in an increase in the elderly population, with older women outnumbering men. As the population ages, it is expected that the majority will be female. In 2021, 86 countries had more men than women, but by 2050, this figure is projected to decrease to 67 countries.

However, the implications of these shifts remain contested. Some researchers, such as Hudson and Den Boer (2004), argue that a surplus of men, particularly young, unmarried men, could lead to increased social instability and violence, as this demographic is often associated with higher levels of aggression and risk-taking behavior, which may currently happen in India or China since there is a 15-35 million male surplus. Others, like Davis et al. (2019), suggest that the demographic shift could lead to an aging population dominated by elderly women, especially in societies with lower fertility rates. This shift could place additional strain on social support systems and necessitate policy adjustments to address the changing needs of the population.

In contrast, McDonald (2013) highlights how gender-equitable policies in economically developed countries, such as those in Europe and North America, have led to more balanced gender ratios. These regions tend to emphasize gender equality and discourage discriminatory practices like selective abortion. The presence of such policies, alongside social norms that promote equal value for male and female

children, contributes to a more stable demographic structure.

Conclusion

In summary, these demographic changes are shaped by a complex interplay of economic, social, climatic, and natural factors, each contributing in distinct ways to shifts in population dynamics. The topic is vast and multifaceted, with ongoing studies aiming to understand the full scope of these influences. However, predicting the outcomes of these changes, or determining whether they will have positive or negative effects on society, remains inherently challenging. Moreover, the interconnected nature of these factors makes it difficult to isolate specific causes or forecast their compounded effects. This complexity underscores the need for continued interdisciplinary research to better understand how these variables interact and to develop more accurate predictive models. Ultimately, the impact of these demographic changes will depend on how societies adapt and respond to emerging challenges, through policy interventions, technological advancements, and social innovation.

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